

Spiritualism

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Entry tags: Religious Group, New Religious Movement (NRM)

In 1948, young sisters Maggie and Katy Fox reported to their family that not only was there a spirit living in their house, but they'd learned how to communicate with it. Friends and neighbors around their house in upstate New York came to bear witness to the spirit's "rappings," the girls quickly became celebrity mediums, and the Spiritualist movement took off. Spiritualism coalesced around a belief that the dead live on in a "spirit world" separated from the world of the living by a thin veil. In this spirit world, individual identities and personal connections persist, and the dead can continue to grow and to spiritually mature. The movement's central practices include seances, trance lectures, mediumship, healings, and other modes of communication with the spirit world. The commercial success of events like public seances and products like Ouija boards have blurred the line between Spiritualism-as-entertainment and Spiritualism-as-religion from the tradition's earliest days. Spiritualists also eschew central organization and have no formal markers of religious affiliation, so no precise figures exist for affiliation. However, scholars estimate that anywhere from 3 to 11 million Americans were participating in Spiritualism at the movement's peak in the late 19th century. Drawing on previous religious traditions like Mesmerism, Swedenborgianism, and New Thought, Spiritualism followed in the iconoclastic footprints of other new religious movements that came out of the Burned-over District in the 19th century. Early Spiritualists denounced dogmatism and sectarianism of organized religion, and spoke out against the Calvinist notion that humankind is innately sinful. In turn, most Christian churches explicitly disavowed Spiritualism, warning congregants that it was a fraud – or worse, that it was witchcraft. Still, many Spiritualists have historically been practicing Christians, and some churches (especially Quaker, Universalist, and Unitarian churches) have either tacitly or even explicitly welcomed Spiritualism as an outgrowth of Christian practice. Some Spiritualists founded churches of their own, and several associations of Spiritualist Churches exist to this day. The movement also had strong ties to social reform movements, including abolition and women's suffrage. Spiritualist practice was originally centered in the northern U.S., with another notable pocket of popularity around New Orleans. English-language periodicals, Spiritualist camps, and travelling mediums also connected American practitioners to a transnational network that grew to extend through Great Britain, parts of Canada. The movement was also briefly in vogue throughout continental Europe. Although Spiritualism experienced another surge of popularity in the wake of WWI, it has never regained its 19th century status in the religious and cultural mainstream.

Date Range: 1848 CE - 2020 CE

Region: North Atlantic Spiritualism

Region tags: North America, Canada, United States of America, Scotland, England, Ireland

This map reflects where the majority of Spiritualist practitioners have been centered, being the United States, Canada, and the British Isles.

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Braude, Ann. 2001. *Radical spirits: Spiritualism and Women's Rights in Nineteenth-Century America*. Bloomington: Indiana University Press.
- Source 2: McGarry, Molly. 2008. *Ghosts of Futures Past: Spiritualism and the Cultural Politics of Nineteenth-Century America*. Berkeley: University of California Press.
- Source 3: Cox, Robert S. 2003. *Body and Soul: a Sympathetic History of American Spiritualism*. Charlottesville: University of Virginia Press.
- Source 1: Faust, Drew Gilpin. 2008. *This Republic of Suffering: Death And the American Civil War*. New York: Alfred A. Knopf.
- Source 2: Albanese, Catherine L. 2007. *A Republic of Mind and Spirit: A Cultural History of American Metaphysical Religion*. New Haven: Yale University Press.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=7YOEznC4WU>
- Source 1 Description: 2018 lecture by historian Dr. Robert Cox. Focuses on Spiritualism's roots in mesmerism, and the movement's ties to social reform. Includes an ethnographic description of a contemporary Spiritualist Church service (49:00 - 55:30).
- Source 2 URL: <https://digital.library.temple.edu/digital/collection/p245801coll10/id/69687/rec/2>
- Source 2 Description: "The Commercialization of the Afterlife: Spiritualism's Supernatural Economy," 2010 master's thesis by Richard W. Fink II. Offers a thorough examination of how 19th century Spiritualism was mass-marketed simultaneously as entertainment and as a path to spiritual growth.
- Source 1 URL: https://www.youtube.com/results?search_query=%23HollywoodMedium
- Source 1 Description: "Hollywood Medium" is an example of how Spiritualist practice continues today through celebrity mediums.
- Source 2 URL: https://www.youtube.com/results?search_query=long+island+medium
- Source 2 Description: "Long Island Medium" offers another vivid example.
- Source 1 URL: <https://www.bbc.co.uk/bbcthree/article/eabdc0ed-70c0-4af2-8295-96ebfc4dc613>
- Source 1 Description: A description of a contemporary British Spiritualist meeting.
- Source 2 URL: <https://goop.com/wellness/spirituality/medium-channels-loved-one-explains-can-connect/>
- Source 2 Description: This article includes an extensive interview with a medium. Its presence on "goop," a lifestyle blog, also shows how Spiritualist practices have been folded into the broad contemporary wellness movement.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 1 URL: <https://nsac.org/>
- Source 1 Description: Database that includes Spiritualist periodicals from around the world, as well as periodicals for related traditions (e.g. Theosophy, New Thought).
- Source 2 URL: <https://nsac.org>
- Source 2 Description: Website of the National Spiritualist Association of Churches, one of several Spiritualist organizations. Includes archived sermons and a directory of member churches.

– Source 3 URL: <http://gutenberg.net.au/ebooks03/0301051h.html#pic11>

– Source 3 Description: Full text of "The History of Spiritualism," by Sir Arthur Conan Doyle, which offers a passionate defense of Spiritualism.

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

↳ Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Many Spiritualist publications denounced organized religion, and in turn, many churches (especially white Protestant churches) explicitly disavowed spiritualism, and warned congregants against it. Occasionally, congregants were excommunicated from Protestant churches for their vocal embrace of Spiritualism. However much this competition played out in print and from the pulpit, though, most Americans did not see Christian and Spiritualist practice as mutually exclusive.

↳ Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Some churches (especially Quaker, Universalist, and Unitarian churches) tacitly or even explicitly welcomed Spiritualism as an outgrowth of Christian practice – as exemplified, for example, by churches inviting mediums to speak from the pulpit. This combinative impulse went both way, with some Spiritualists establishing churches based on a Protestant model. See this online tour of a Spiritualist camp, which begins with a rendition of "Amazing Grace," to see the way that Christian imagery and music is woven into Spiritualist practice: <https://campchesterfield.net/take-a-tour/>

↳ Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

Notes: In spite of the tensions between mainstream Christianity and Spiritualism, the consumer culture around Spiritualism was often simply playful. Seances were treated by some Americans as a parlor game, and Spiritualist language became part of a cultural vernacular. See the attached sheet music for a song called "Spirit Rappings" for an example of how Spiritualism was reflected in the culture of the late 19th century.

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Notes: Although some Spiritualists can be identified through membership in a formal Spiritualist Church, participation in Spiritualist camps, or public practice of mediumship, many others have affiliated themselves with the religion simply by participating in spiritualist practices, whether privately or publicly. There are no formal markers of entry into the community.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Notes: Spiritualists denounce sectarianism and dogmatism, and don't seek to win "converts" in an exclusive sense. However, in the face of heavily publicized attempts by skeptics to debunk mediumship, Spiritualists have historically sought to prove the scientific veracity of their claims through demonstrations of mediumship, as well as by inviting investigation by skeptics.

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Low estimates of Spiritualist numbers suggest that there were perhaps 3 million participants at the movement's peak in the late 1800s; other estimates put that number as high as 11 million. This question mark in the historical record largely reflects the fact that there is no formal marker of affiliation with the movement.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral

scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: There are no Spiritualist scriptures, although Andrew Jackson Davis' work at times came close to achieving that status in some Spiritualist congregations.

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Some public spaces

Notes: The sunflower was adopted as a symbol of Spiritualism in the 1890's, and it can still be seen at Spiritualist camps and Spiritualists' homes, as well as featured prominently on Spiritualist web-pages and promotional materials.

Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The material body is often metaphorically referred to in Spiritualist literature as clothing that the spirit sheds upon death. The spirit is understood to continue growing and maturing after the death of the physical body, and to gain access to knowledge that it could not access while in the physical world.

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Spiritualist understandings of the afterlife are the lynchpin of the tradition as a whole. Spiritualists believe that there is no hell; only higher or lower heavens that are placed in concentric celestial spheres. This cosmological model, a twist on Swedenborg's, was outlined by Andrew Jackson Davis. The lowest of the spheres, which is mostly populated by those who have recently died, is known as the "Summerland." (Albanese, 259; Cox, 101). Every human who dies passes into the Summerland. There is no punishment in the afterlife; all spirits progress towards perfection. The societal organization in these spheres mirrors that on earth, but perfected. Spirits can continue to develop the passions and talents that drove them while they were alive by participating in commerce, education, the arts, and politics (Cox, 105). This vision of the afterlife is understood by historians to be a direct rejoinder to dominant Calvinist theologies of predestination of the early 19th century that offered little solace in the face of death - especially to parents who had lost of infants and children, and whose grief was compounded by anxieties around eternal damnation. It is unsurprising that this vision of the afterlife held mass appeal in the decades following the Civil War and in the years after WWI.

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The exact location of the afterlife was a fixation for some prominent early Spiritualists. Chemist and Spiritualist Robert Hare, for example, specified that the heavenly spheres existed 60 to 120 miles above the earth's surface. This preoccupation with location makes sense, given Spiritualists' strong identification as a movement built on scientific investigation and discovery. However, most Spiritualists were more interested what everyday life in the spirit world looked like, describing everything from the spirit world's nurseries (Braude, 40) to its political structures (in which, reportedly, figures like George Washington and Benjamin Franklin continued to play leading roles; Cox, 144) to its division into separate societies along racial lines (Albanese, 241).

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Notes: To greater or lesser degrees of specificity, Spiritualists describe the afterlife as playing out in concentric spheres around the earth. This was originally outlined by Andrew Jackson Davis, who drew heavily on Swedenborg's descriptions of the heavens (Albanese, 259).

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined "above" space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: Spiritualists believe that upon death, human spirits pass to the spirit world where they continue to grow and morally evolve. Although spirits can visit the material world, they are never again housed in material bodies.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: Although bodies are still buried in a range of culturally normative ways (i.e. cremated or interred), they are regarded as material shells drained of any connection to the spirit.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Burial customs fall within the range of culturally normative practices in America and the UK, with slight if any differences (e.g. the language of the funeral sermon or of the tombstone). See the attached images of gravestones from the Historic Congressional Cemetery in Washington, D.C.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: A supreme divinity is referenced by Spiritualists, but infrequently. When it is, it is framed as imbuing all of nature and flowing through every soul, a singular energy that connects all things, a cosmic intelligence. Generally avoiding anthropomorphism, Spiritualists framed God as representing a balance between masculine and feminine. Spiritualist texts typically leave ample room for practitioners of other faiths to fill in the specifics of a divinity they worship. Framing their communication with spirits as in-line with the natural order, Spiritualists generally reject the notion of a God who has to actively intercede in history in miraculous ways.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: The god of Spiritualism, when it is explicitly discussed, is framed a pure and totalizing intelligence. It is at times referred to as the "infinite intelligence." Although it does not "watch" humankind's behavior in order to punish or reward, it is omniscient.

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
 - Notes: The god of Spiritualism is not passive, but is rather an energy that flows throughout the universe and drives the eternal motion of progress. However, it does not directly, personally intervene in human affairs. Rather, spirits draw on their privileged knowledge of the divine to gently intervene in human minds.
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - No
 - Notes: The divine is described as pure love and connectedness. However, these are stable traits rather than positive emotions that a divine entity is feelings, and that can be contrasted to negative emotions.
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - No
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - No

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Notes: Worship is simply not prescribed by Spiritualism; participants may worship one god, multiple divine beings, or none at all.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Notes: For Spiritualists, God communicates through the natural world; by looking to the inviolable natural law, Spiritualists can come to understand the divine order of the universe. They can also understand it by communicating with spirits. This is not because there is a personal God who passes on individuated messages through spirits, but rather because spirits are on a different plane of existence, and therefore have access to greater knowledge about the divine underpinnings of the cosmos. Jesus was framed as a human moral teacher who simply exemplified Spiritualist practice; one 19th century Spiritualist, Abraham Pierce, described him as "Jesus, the Great Medium" (Cox, 101).

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, through nature, self-reflection, and spirit communications.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: Dreams of spirits are understood to carry messages of the divine truth.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Again, this is indirect communication; through trance, some mediums are able to travel through the spheres, to consult with spirits, and to perceive divine truths that would otherwise be hidden from mortal eyes.

↳ Through divination practices:

– No

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

↳ Only through monarch

– No

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Nature

Notes: In Spiritualism, the divine communicates with the living through Nature, and through unfolding scientific discovery. Unlike human spirits, the divine does not need a vocabulary to communicate. It saturates the world around us, and it is the job of every individual to learn to attune themselves to it. This is very similar to Transcendentalist notions of the divine.

– Yes [specify]: Introspection

Notes: Also in a Transcendentalist vein, Spiritualism teaches that God can be accessed by looking within. Spiritualist Abby Sewall wrote in the 1850's that true faith "could only be found by retiring into the secret chamber of the soul, and there finding all of heaven that will ever do us any good here or hereafter" (Cox, 78).

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Notes: Some Spiritualists describe seeing vivid visions of spirits, and can describe what they are wearing, what they are doing, and what they look like. Spirit photographs, which were briefly popular in the late 19th century, purported to use technological developments to reveal the presence of the dead around us. In turn of the century mediumship, visible ectoplasm and lights during seances were also thought to be ways in which spirits could visibly manifest.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Notes: Touching is often a part of seances, and has been since early in the Spiritualist movement. In 1854, for example, William Lloyd Garrison was at a séance when the medium announced that Jesse Hutchinson, of the famous musical family, was present. Garrison asked Hutchinson to grasp his hand, and then felt a cold touch that he was convinced was the spirit's. (Braude, 17).

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: As they progress through the spheres, spirits gain knowledge and insight about the past, present, and future. Generally, those in the closest sphere are those who have most recently died, and who are therefore most pre-occupied with earthly connections.

Generally, spirits are understood to keep watch over their own families or loved ones, and to have a super-human range of knowledge about them. Spirit-guides (though their existence is contested within Spiritualism) are spirits that commit themselves to specific individuals, gently guiding them on a course of moral growth and wisdom.

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Notes: The notion that the human mind, emotions, and character becomes transparent to spirits has been a part of Spiritualism since its early days. Early Spiritualist Joel Tiffany wrote that spirits “manifest a power to read the thoughts, feelings, and emotions which are concealed deep in the recesses of the soul” (Cox, 95). Spirits are generally reported to use this knowledge to bring peace, wisdom, and reassurance to the living. For an example of a spirit’s knowledge of his living sister’s guilt play out in a contemporary setting, see this video: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=m42cYFYDAzw>

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Spirits are understood to perceive truths that appear murky from a human vantage point, and the character of individual humans is one of those truths. However, because spirits are working within a frame of eternal moral

progress, they also have the perspective to see that character flaws are not permanent.

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Notes: In some Spiritualist practice, future predictions about individuals' lives are somewhat vague, and nested inside narratives about the coming establishment of world peace, for instance, or other meta-narratives. However, some are also very specific. See this vice article for a contemporary description of a sitting with a medium who learns from spirits that her client, the author of the article, will be traveling to Barbados and to Beijing in the near future: https://www.vice.com/en_us/article/nn4g87/inside-cassadaga

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

–Yes [specify]: Spirits can also learn about the world from one another.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Spirits may interact with the physical world (e.g. tables, planchettes) to assert their presence and communicate. They intervene in human affairs only by encouraging the living along paths of progress. Early Spiritualist Isaac Post wrote, "Let no man claim that he has made great improvements in the arts and sciences, unassisted by spirit friends." (Cox, 105).

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Notes: Spirits can work in the world by giving suggestions or directions to the living. They can also effect physical change by manipulating objects, like ouija boards.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: This is a key Spiritualist belief: that individual identities, memories, personalities, and connections persist after the death of the body.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Notes: Although spirits hypothetically could exhibit negative emotions, within

Spiritualist literature they are overwhelmingly happy in their lives in the "Summerland", optimistic about the progressive moral evolution of the mortal world, and trusting that their loved ones will also be delivered into a blissful spirit world upon death.

↳ Human spirits possess hunger:

– No

↳ Human spirits possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Babies and children who met untimely deaths continue to mature to adulthood in the spirit world.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Spiritualist mediums often report being "interrupted" by spirits outside of the bounds of formal seances, as they go about their daily lives. For a contemporary example of this, see this clip of the Long Island Medium: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GcKf3DG-LEk> This has been the case from the beginning of the movement, when the silence of the Fox family's home was interrupted by strange rappings. At most seances, audiences are also awake and in normal states as they communicate with spirits. Although mediums carefully attune to the voices of spirits during seances, they do not necessarily need to be in a trance state to communicate with them.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: For example, 19th century Spiritualist poet Fanny Green reported that her brother had come to her in a dream and described the joys of the Summerland, comforting her and asking her to pass along his message to his parents. (Braude, 51-52). For a contemporary medium's discussion of spirit visitation during dreams, see this blog entry by Rebecca Rosen: <https://www.rebeccarosen.com/rebeccarosenblog/2014/5/21/how-spirits-communicate-in-our-dreams>

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: Some Spiritualists report being put into a trance by spirits unwittingly. Famous medium Cora Scott said that she was first made aware of her gift for mediumship when as a young girl she went into a trance in the garden one day, and woke up having transcribed a letter addressed to her mother in the voice of a long-dead aunt. However, entering trance is a skill that can also be

cultivated. In the 19th century, some mediums were understood to be so gifted at entering trance and functioning as ventriloquists for spirits that they could deliver entire lectures while in trance. Historical figures were able to speak again through them, from Benjamin Franklin to Edgar Allen Poe. The largely female ranks of trance lectures stand as a sign of Spiritualism's complex relationship with feminism; female trance lecturers were able to deliver speeches to male audiences, but they had to do so by channeling male voices. For a contemporary medium's explanation of trance, click here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OPBVlznzTUO> For video of an interview with a spirit, Jonathan, while his medium is in trance, click here: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=073U46anPWI>

↳ Through divination processes:
– No

↳ Only through specialists:
– No

Notes: Although Spiritualists believe that some people were naturally gifted mediums, they also believe that any practitioner can attune their senses, perceive messages from the spirit world, and draw on the wisdom revealed by the spirit world to achieve spiritual balance.

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

↳ Communicate with living through other means:
– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– No

Notes: Although Spiritualists often use the term "angels," they generally use it to mean hyper-evolved forms of the human spirit. Some Spiritualists believe in other supernatural beings (for example, Spiritualist Sir Arthur Conan Doyle famously believed in fairies), but those beliefs are not specified by Spiritualism.

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:
– No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it

relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Notes: Spirits can observe their loved ones who are still in the world of the living. They can also see across time and space, and can hypothetically observe anyone. However, they are not preoccupied with surveilling. The closest thing to this would be Spirit-Guides.

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Notes: Although a general sense of progressive perfectionism pervades Spiritualism, it is not formalized into an eschatology. Some 19th century Spiritualists drew on the language of dispensationalism to describe their own times as a new epoch of spiritual progress (Cox, 144). Andrew Jackson Davis elaborated a theology in which when all spirits reached the zeniths of their progression through the spheres, the whole structure would implode and be remade as a new series of spheres to be travelled through (Albanese, 260). However, this part of Davis's vision did not gain much traction with the broader Spiritualist community. What Albanese describes as "a theology of eternal progress" means that no grand finale is needed (Albanese, 266).

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present (but not emphasized)

Notes: Things like dress, burial customs, food, etiquette, etc. are all understood by Spiritualists to be cultural norms rather than spiritual. Even religious norms like what we call God and how

we worship are understood to be flexible and acculturated. These are not generally discussed. Instead, Spiritualists focus on universal moral principles like truth, love, equality, and freedom of conscience.

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– Yes

Notes: Moral norms of love and truth are linked to the order of the cosmos. The entire cosmos is understood to be on a progressive path towards perfect truth. If practitioners can participate in that progress towards moral perfection while they are on earth, they will have further to travel to reach the highest sphere in the spirit world.

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– No

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

↳ Moral norms apply to:

- All individuals within society
- All individuals within contemporary world
- All individuals (any time period)

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: In fact, Spiritualists were generally advocates for marriage reform to increase freedom of sexual expression. Some Spiritualists were outspoken in favor of free love. As detailed by Molly McGarry (Chapter 3 of *Ghosts of Futures Past: "Spectral Sexualities: Free Love, Moral Panic, and the Making of U.S. Obscenity Law"*), Spiritualists were divided over how strongly and in what ways to embrace the idea of free love. Some argued that finding the right spiritual mate was more important than respecting the bounds of legal marriage. Others compared marriage to slavery, calling for it to be remade as an egalitarian partnership that could be dissolved at will. Harmonia, a short-lived 1850's Spiritualist commune in Battle Creek, Michigan, dissolved in part because of the animosity it faced from neighbors over its free love underpinnings.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Notes: Egalitarianism and compassion form an ethical base for Spiritualists. Many Spiritualists, though not all, see their religion as a mandate for social reforms, particularly those that would increase equality and the freedom of individual expression.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: Spiritualism's foundational rituals - seances, trance lectures, healings, and, sometimes, formal church services - all require at least a small group of people, including a medium to facilitate communication with the spirit world. However, especially since there is no one ritual action that defines membership in Spiritualism, it is possible to be a Spiritualist but opt out of this public or communal engagement.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, through the government.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, through the government, non-profits, and other religious organizations.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, through the government, non-profits, and other religious organizations.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Notes: There are a few examples of Spiritualist communities that established their own independent schools. For example, one was founded in Harmonia, a utopian Spiritualist community in Battle Creek, MI.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Notes: Spiritualist churches (and church associations) inevitably have some bureaucracy, but many adherents aren't associated with a church.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: They interact with governmental bureaucracies. If they are members of other religions, they also potentially interact with the bureaucracies of those religious institutions.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, by the government.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, by the government.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, by the government, as well as potentially by other religious traditions in which they are members.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, governmental police forces.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, governmental.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Yes, the English language was used throughout governmental institutions, as well as through other religious institutions.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Spiritualists used, and continue to use, the Gregorian calendar.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Certainly some Spiritualists get food assistance from the government, from other religious institutions, or through nonprofits.